

zarządzanie łańcuchem dostaw (Supply Chain Management), optymalizacja transportu miejskiego, pojazdy autonomiczne i zaawansowane systemy wspomaganie, transport kosmiczny oraz lotnictwo, wirtualna/rozszerzona rzeczywistość (VR/AR), ekologia, opieka zdrowotna oraz cyberbezpieczeństwo.

Pomimo istotnych zalet komputerów kwantowych oraz ich zastosowania, istnieje także szereg barier, które mogą opóźnić w czasie kolejne stopnie wprowadzania technologii, o których mowa w artykule. Pomimo tego, dobrze jest stopniowo rozwijać oraz przygotowywać przez firmy dogodne warunki do przyszłego rozwoju generalnie cyfryzacji, z potencjalną możliwością zastosowanie komputerów kwantowych.

6. Rysunki

Rys. 1 Różnica między bitem a kubitem, grafika własna

Rys. 2 Grafika symbolizująca płytkę PCB komputera, grafika własna

Rys. 3 Big data by Mateusz Brejnak, Unsplash, <https://unsplash.com/photos/N0hRiSsNjv0>, data dostępu 17.08.2022 r.

Rys. 4 Spedycja/transport by Mateusz Brejnak, Unsplash, <https://unsplash.com/photos/qAGIOV12zqk>, data dostępu 17.08.2022 r.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND BLOCKCHAIN FOR NEUROSCIENCE

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Abstract

The two-way links between neuroscience and artificial intelligence are considered. On the one hand, neuroscience data is the source of development of artificial intelligence. On the other hand, artificial intelligence helps to diagnose and treat neurological diseases. The possibility of expanding the application of artificial intelligence in alliance with blockchain technology to control the correctness of the use of neuroscience data, to recognise neuromyths and to counteract their proliferation has been considered.

Keywords: neuroscience, artificial intelligence, blockchain, neuromyths.

It is well known that the development of artificial intelligence is largely determined by advances in neuroscience. Advances in artificial intelligence are making it possible to improve the treatment and diagnosis of neurological diseases, improve the quality of the neurologist's work and reduce the number of errors. However, the ability of artificial intelligence, together with blockchain, to counter speculative interpretations of neuroscience data remains little explored [4,7].

When we hear the phrase 'artificial intelligence', we imagine robots, the neurointernet, self-directed transport, universal chipisation... But let us not forget that all of these artificial intelligence hotspots are made possible by the breakthrough development of neuroscience.

Neuroscience is a collective term that developed spontaneously. The group of neuroscience includes neurobiology, neurogenetics, neurophysiology and neuropharmacology. It also includes neuropsychology,

psychophysiology, cognitive science... All of them have something to do with the brain.

Neuroscience today means work in the field of artificial intelligence, unique gene therapy for inherited diseases of the nervous system, and fundamentally new approaches to Parkinson's disease, epilepsy, Alzheimer's disease and migraine based on gene expression control. This is a new era of drugs that can inhibit and even completely block nerve cell death after acute and chronic damage to the brain and spinal cord. Impressive progress is also being made in the development of imaging techniques for the living brain, its blood flow, electrical activity and structure. One day, these technologies may allow us to communicate with unconscious patients. Brain-machine interfaces have emerged. Neurocomputer interfaces aim to restore sight, hearing, motor abilities, and the ability to communicate to sick people. These technologies make it possible to transform the power of thought into the movements of prosthetic parts of immobilised patients, for example, to imitate arm movement. Ways of treating neurodegenerative diseases and brain tumours with stem cells are being actively developed. This would have been something out of the realm of science fiction only a short time ago! [5]

Neuroscience owes much of its success to the use of artificial intelligence. The end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st century has brought forth a veritable wave of neurological diseases. How do we cope with the stresses of the information age? Headaches, neuralgias, strokes, weather addiction, increase in neuropsychiatric causes of disability Artificial Intelligence can reduce the neurological load on humans by taking over routine, strenuous or time-consuming mental operations. Artificial intelligence, unlike humans, does not tire and helps relieve human fatigue, reduces occupational errors, reduces the workload for humans, and increases productivity and ergonomics [11].

However, the area of application of artificial intelligence combined with blockchain in the field of popularisation of neuroscience knowledge remains little explored, in order to reduce the dangers associated with the myths that are born around them.

Today, neuroscience does not only deal with neurologically ill patients. It is also useful for healthy people who are thinking about discovering their abilities, improving their learning, choosing a profession based on their personality, preventing diseases, and prolonging their lives. Neuropsychology, for example, makes it possible to find the causes of learning difficulties, to find effective ways of overcoming them and to build optimal individual learning paths. Where teachers apply the knowledge of neuropsychology, the quality of education improves, children become less tired, and the risk of developing chronic emotional stress, which, in its turn, provokes psychosomatic disorders, decreases. The potential of neuropsychology for education, however, is far from exhausted!

The practical value of the neurosciences lies first and foremost in specifying the permissible limits of pedagogy (restrictions, taboos that must not be crossed), formulating the laws of the brain that must not

contradict the learning process ("the ecological imperative of pedagogy").

In some countries, for example, classes start quite early. But research in neurobiology has shown that adolescent sleep differs significantly from adult sleep, both in duration and structure. As a result, some US states have shifted the start of school to later in the day.

However, the current lack of public awareness of neuroscience creates fertile ground for myths and misconceptions, which are exploited by unscrupulous commercial entities.

John Bruer, Sue White and other eminent scientists believe that for literally every true breakthrough in neuroscience, there is a "neuro-noise". It could be overlooked if it did not harm people and discredit scientific discoveries! Irresponsible, amateurish extrapolation of basic research into the field of education generates neuro-myths [1,8].

Many of the neurobiological legends have gone 'out into the wild' before the facts being disseminated have been double-checked. And even if verification disproved the original results, the myths lived on. Thus the transition from scientific data to misinformation took place. It is amazing that many school teachers around the world believe in myths about how the human brain works [3].

For example, who hasn't heard that people are right-hemispheric (creative) and left-hemispheric (logical)? If a teacher concludes that a student is 'right brain', this can be used as an indulgence for failing a maths test. Unfortunately, hemispheric tests are sometimes used even in universities and for job applications....

Why is this wrong? Because the functions of the hemispheres have been studied on epileptic patients with surgically split hemispheres, and the results have been transferred to healthy people. Even the idea was born that there are two different brains, each with its own sensations and peculiarities of mental processes. One hemisphere dominates the other. Neuropsychologists still have to refute these views.

Science proves that there is a complex combination of right-left dominance of hands, eyes, feet, ways of receiving information, processing it, transforming it, etc. In addition, it turns out that this or that dominance is not constant over time! It changes adaptively to the external conditions of living and the organism's inner needs. For example, in a right-handed child, the activity of the left hand increases adaptively at the beginning of the school year. Among people living in the north or in environmentally disadvantaged areas, the left eye and left ear are more likely to be dominant. The leading eye or ear may change when taking hormonal medication, moving to a new place of residence, etc. That is, the body, as a self-regulating system, balances the ratio of right and left, providing optimal vitality in specific conditions. Therefore, such asymmetry is called functional asymmetry. Combined with other psychophysiological and personal characteristics it determines school adaptation, adaptability to the climate, success in a particular sport, preference for a particular learning system, ways of mastering a foreign language ...

As far as learning success is concerned, anyone can do well. The uniqueness of the body is that it can activate its reserves when necessary. Knowledge of such reserves may be useful for every person to make informed decisions in various life situations.

We will not dwell on other neuromyths, they are well described in scientific literature [6,9].

It is paradoxical that against the background of unrealisation of huge possibilities of neuroscience, which lie on the surface, the Internet is swarming with commercial offers of "supernova" methods of learning, appealing to data in electroencephalography, magnetic resonance, computer and positron emission tomography of brain, promising fast effect!

A closer look reveals that the "neuro" wrapper of the "new" methods is nothing more than a publicity stunt. Nothing new is being proposed compared to what has long been known to pedagogy.

Such proposals are not only dangerous for our wallet. Blinded by the successes of neuroscience, we should not forget about the protection of childhood, about children's health. Neurobiological data have become actively used to justify any dubious ideas. It is enough to add "neuro" to the word, and it begins to look very modern, and takes away from direct criticism. Here and there flicker new terms "neuro: neuropedagogy, neurogeography, neuroanime, neuroleadership, etc. At the origins of neuromyths are attempts by "popularizers" to link scientific data about the functioning of synapses (connections) of nerve cells with the personality of learners. In doing so, the results of a single brain study can be easily extrapolated to the entire population; data obtained in animals to humans; the results of an adult study to a child.

According to researchers, 56% of educators are victims of neuroboom. But while neurobiology deals with the brain at the molecular and cellular level, in pedagogy we deal with psycho-social and socio-cultural phenomena, and the language of "translation" of natural science knowledge at the cellular level into humanitarian knowledge at the personality level has not yet been created. In neuroscience research, all brain functions are studied in isolation for simplicity, and the nervous system as a whole, functioning as a unit, is not considered. Despite great advances in modern interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research, the integrative paradigm of anthropology is still far from complete. A single interdisciplinary science of the brain has yet to be established. Despite its rapid growth, this science is still in its relative infancy with regard to the study of the healthy brain, and therefore educational researchers should wait. Unfortunately, neuromyths continue to be widely 'sold' to teachers, administrators and the public. The popular simplification of scientific information runs the risk of turning it into false information [9].

It is important that digitalization of education, including the rapid spread of distance learning, creates long-term resources for global and national educational development, overcomes barriers to the introduction of educational technologies with proven safety, and stimulates the development of educational systems.

For example, blockchain technology opens up fundamentally new opportunities for the educational

system and forms the conditions for the educational system to reach a qualitatively new level of development [8].

Attention to the problems of using blockchain technology in the educational system is associated with its ability to collect information, store it in an unchanged form, control the reliability of data, create rules and methodologies for management activities. In this regard, its use in the education system, according to researchers and practitioners, can significantly improve the quality of educational services and, in the future, facilitate the unimpeded exchange of information, technologies and pedagogical methods at the global level to promote the educational systems of all countries in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

We believe that an alliance of artificial intelligence and blockchain can help in this direction. After all, it is necessary to process large amounts of data, to systematise, to control the 'red' line of experiments in education, which must not be crossed under any circumstances, because the laws of the brain are objective. An artificial intelligence neural network works on the same principle as a neural network in a living organism. It allows to distinguish one object from another, to compare, analyse, distinguish mood, functional state of a person, monitor safety, record the number of movements necessary to optimise the brain work of students, be an intellectual assistant to a teacher.

Digitalisation of education, including the rapid spread of distance learning, should create long-term resources for global and national education, overcome barriers to the adoption of educational technology with proven safety and put barriers in place to counterfeit techniques and technologies.

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АНАЛИЗ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ АТМОСФЕРОСТОЙКИХ СТАЛЕЙ

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ANALYSIS OF WEATHER-RESISTANT STEELS CHARACTERISTICS

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Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены основные особенности атмосферостойких сталей. Отмечена актуальность разработки технологий изготовления стального проката, отличающегося стойкостью к атмосферной коррозии. Отдельное внимание уделено анализу влияния химического состава на стойкость стали к атмосферной коррозии.